

Transportation Consortium of South-Central States

Solving Emerging Transportation Resiliency, Sustainability, and Economic Challenges through the Use of Innovative Materials and Construction Methods: From Research to Implementation

Development of a Low Power, Low Cost Rural Railway Intersection Smart Detection and Warning System

Project No. 19SAUTSA03

Lead University: University of Texas at San Antonio

Final Report
November 2020

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16. Abstract <p>This project explores a different approach to provide preemptive warning for train detection at grade-crossings to increase safety and reduce motor vehicle congestion. The development of a novel, low cost, low power, and off rail right-of-way (ROW) detection and warning system will be presented. A background of track circuits, which is the rail industries standard for train detection, will also be provided to highlight the benefits and challenges of the rail industry installing a system at every grade-crossings that lack any type of active warning. The benefits of using thermal imaging instead of traditional video for computer vision will also be discussed. Then, the development of a detection algorithm using convolutional neural networks and deep learning methods on a custom dataset of images created by two different thermal sensors will be overviewed. The two sensors tested are the MLX90640 and FLIR Lepton 3.0. Both react to heat radiation emitted from objects but in very different ways from a technology perspective. This difference in technology creates a large gap in cost and power between the two and was therefore worth testing to analyze the trade off in accuracy achieved in creating an outdoor detection model. Finally, the wireless communication between the detection and warning devices is discussed as well as the network communication for detected data to be logged to an online server and updated on a mobile application. Testing was done at a location approximately one mile east of the Kirby Union Pacific Railyard in San Antonio, TX from a distance that was off the property of ROW.</p>			
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SI* (MODERN METRIC) CONVERSION FACTORS

APPROXIMATE CONVERSIONS TO SI UNITS

Symbol	When You Know	Multiply By	To Find	Symbol
LENGTH				
in	inches	25.4	millimeters	mm
ft	feet	0.305	meters	m
yd	yards	0.914	meters	m
mi	miles	1.61	kilometers	km
AREA				
in ²	square inches	645.2	square millimeters	mm ²
ft ²	square feet	0.093	square meters	m ²
yd ²	square yard	0.836	square meters	m ²
ac	acres	0.405	hectares	ha
mi ²	square miles	2.59	square kilometers	km ²
VOLUME				
fl oz	fluid ounces	29.57	milliliters	mL
gal	gallons	3.785	liters	L
ft ³	cubic feet	0.028	cubic meters	m ³
yd ³	cubic yards	0.765	cubic meters	m ³
NOTE: volumes greater than 1000 L shall be shown in m ³				
MASS				
oz	ounces	28.35	grams	g
lb	pounds	0.454	kilograms	kg
T	short tons (2000 lb)	0.907	megagrams (or "metric ton")	Mg (or "t")
TEMPERATURE (exact degrees)				
°F	Fahrenheit	5 (F-32)/9 or (F-32)/1.8	Celsius	°C
ILLUMINATION				
fc	foot-candles	10.76	lux	lx
fl	foot-Lamberts	3.426	candela/m ²	cd/m ²
FORCE and PRESSURE or STRESS				
lbf	poundforce	4.45	newtons	N
lbf/in ²	poundforce per square inch	6.89	kilopascals	kPa

APPROXIMATE CONVERSIONS FROM SI UNITS

Symbol	When You Know	Multiply By	To Find	Symbol
LENGTH				
mm	millimeters	0.039	inches	in
m	meters	3.28	feet	ft
m	meters	1.09	yards	yd
km	kilometers	0.621	miles	mi
AREA				
mm ²	square millimeters	0.0016	square inches	in ²
m ²	square meters	10.764	square feet	ft ²
m ²	square meters	1.195	square yards	yd ²
ha	hectares	2.47	acres	ac
km ²	square kilometers	0.386	square miles	mi ²
VOLUME				
mL	milliliters	0.034	fluid ounces	fl oz
L	liters	0.264	gallons	gal
m ³	cubic meters	35.314	cubic feet	ft ³
m ³	cubic meters	1.307	cubic yards	yd ³
MASS				
g	grams	0.035	ounces	oz
kg	kilograms	2.202	pounds	lb
Mg (or "t")	megagrams (or "metric ton")	1.103	short tons (2000 lb)	T
TEMPERATURE (exact degrees)				
°C	Celsius	1.8C+32	Fahrenheit	°F
ILLUMINATION				
lx	lux	0.0929	foot-candles	fc
cd/m ²	candela/m ²	0.2919	foot-Lamberts	fl
FORCE and PRESSURE or STRESS				
N	newtons	0.225	poundforce	lbf
kPa	kilopascals	0.145	poundforce per square inch	lbf/in ²

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This project was inspired by the need of a low cost and low power alternative to provide an active warning system at grade-crossings only equipped with passive signage in order to increase the safety for motorists. With the experience obtained through participating in the National Science Foundation's I-Corps program, it was determined from interviews with over 50 industry leaders in the rail industry that the best approach to achieve this would be a detection device that can achieve a high accuracy from a distance off the rail right-of-way. Research was conducted on existing train detection systems used by the rail industry in the U.S as well as detection devices that have been tested through research and development reports to have a better idea on how to achieve this while reducing the maintenance required as well as the number of false detection occurrences due to environmental conditions. With advancements in computer vision using convolutional neural networks (CNN) and deep learning models, video surveillance seemed the most optimal approach to reduce the amount of false detections from far distances. However, video imaging is reluctant in adverse weather conditions and require lighting at all times. Therefore, a thermal approach was taken for the fact that a heat signature is still visible in a wider variety of weather conditions. Heat spots were analyzed on different parts of a moving train with an E30bx FLIR thermal camera to determine what parts would remain above ambient temperatures and provide a consistent mean of detection in changing outdoor conditions. The MLX90640 and FLIR Lepton 3.0, two thermal sensors that differed in price and technology, were used to provide a custom dataset of thermal images to train a detection model using CNN and DNN architectures. Communication between detection and warning devices was made using radio frequency. In addition, communication to an online server using 4G/LTE mobile satellite connection to update logged detection data to a mobile application to provide further preemptive warning than at the grade-crossing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Railroads are one of the oldest means of transportation known to man and therefore, their infrastructures have been established long before any road or highway. Unfortunately for drivers, this means trains have the right-of-way not only in the perspective of seniority but also because of its size and weight. It is physically, and costly, more challenging for a train to stop than it is for a vehicle. As of March 2015, in the U.S. there are 129,470 public grade crossings and of those crossings 59,262, or 46%, consist of a passive warning device. Passive crossings lack any type of active warning or control system, whether it is an activated rail-arm gate or a flashing beacon, to alert motorists of an approaching train. Every year within the last decade, more than 400 rail-related fatalities occur with 28% of these at passive grade crossings (1). Aggressive driving is strongly linked to grade crossing safety with influencing factors such as age, sex, and most importantly, time of day. Drivers do not want to wait and this becomes more evident during the hours people are normally going to and from work (2). The comprehensive cost per death, comprehensive being the accumulated amount of economic loss of life, loss of property, law suits, etc., is estimated at \$10,855,000 (3). That equates to a total loss of \$1,215,760,000 at passive crossings each year.

The standard train detection system for the rail industry in the United States are track circuits which require installation within the tracks and access to commercial power. These systems range anywhere between \$100k-\$200k depending if it is a single or double track application (4). Because of this, the cost of installation and maintaining such systems is not a viable option for every grade crossing that does not meet a traffic volume threshold. This alone creates a need for an off-track detection system for the rail industry to adopt. Although track circuits are not the only form of train detection systems that are commercialized today, they are the only type that can offer years

of proven fail-safe characteristics. The term fail-safe is used to describe the state of a system in which a malfunction occurs. Meaning, if a power outage occurs or the circuit is grounded and/or damaged in any way the state of the system will proceed to warn motorists as if a train is approaching and thus, fail in a safe manner. With the advancements in sensor technologies and detection algorithms, a low cost, off-track and rail-right-of-away detection and warning system approach for government agencies and municipalities to adopt for motorist safety is a more feasible approach rather than relying on the rail industry to adopt new technology.

2. OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this research is to develop a low cost alternative for grade crossing detection and warning systems suitable at any area, even power restricted rural areas. To achieve this, the system must detect trains from off the railway and create an active signage to alert motorists. The system designed will require minimal maintenance as well as provide reduction in the rate of false detections. The system main features would include: detecting the direction of travel, if the train has stopped, and determine the velocity of the train to obtain a constant warning time (CWT). The proposed detection system will use thermal imaging which will utilize the heat signature of the wheel and axles of a train as a means of detection. The proposed system consists of four detection modules as shown in Figure 1; two on each approaching direction of the railway to the intersecting road and placed approximately 7 ft from the center of the tracks; according to the standard minimum operating clearances issued by Union Pacific Railroad Engineering Standard 0038L (5). The system will also include two warning modules on both sides of the roadway intersection and these detection and warning modules will communicate together through radio frequency (RF) modules. The detection happens as follows: as a train approaches the railway intersection, the first detection module furthest from the roadway will detect the train using image processing and detection algorithm. The second detection will be placed at a fixed distance from the leading module and detect the train using the same algorithm. The purpose of the second detection module is to determine the velocity of the oncoming train by calculating the difference in time from the first detection. The second module will also serve as a safety net in situations where the first, or the second, malfunction. The modules will communicate amongst one another using radio frequency. After the speed is determined, the amount of time the beacon will need to

flash will be determined using the speed to provide a constant warning time for various types of trains that travel at different speeds.

Figure 1. Proposed System Architecture

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

The following sections analyze different types of train detection technologies and are categorized as either track circuit or off-track systems. A brief background of track circuits is given to help understand what features are standard and required for the railroad industry since the track circuits are the oldest detection systems. Then the off-track systems are analyzed to highlight what features help reduce cost and false detections.

3.1 Track Circuits

The first type of train detection was developed in 1872 and since then, every new system used by the rail industry has been some sort of an optimized version of this type. The original train detection system was the DC track circuit, illustrated in Figure 2, where the rails are utilized for a current to pass through a section of the tracks defined by rubber insulated joints on opposite ends of the section.

Figure 2. First Means of DC Track Circuit

The current is provided by a power source, that requires a containment housing, and a relay is integrated within the track circuit which serves as a switch for the warning system. When a train enters the section, the wheels and axle provide an alternate route for the current to travel causing the circuit to short and the relay to flip and provide current for the warning device. Over time,

advancements in the DC circuit enabled the system to determine a train's direction and speed to provide a constant warning time (CWT). A CWT is the key for managing driver behavior because it allows the warning system to activate with a consistent delay for trains traveling at varying speeds. Although to do so, it requires additional sections of the track circuit to be implemented onto the railway as shown in Figure 3. This allows the system to monitor which approaching zone the train has entered and determine the speed by calculating how long it takes to cross each section. Implementing multiple sections results in a high number of components and system complexity, making DC circuits high in cost. Also, in urban areas where electrified railways are present the DC circuit cannot be used due to interference with existing current. To counter this flaw, the AC track circuit was developed.

Figure 3. Sectioned DC Track Circuit for Monitoring Speed and Direction

AC track circuits operate in the same way as DC track circuits but are not vulnerable and/or harmful to existing currents. The AC signal is provided by a transformer in the range of 50Hz to 150Hz and in order to energize the relay that sets off the warning circuit, a rectifier is used to transform the AC signal to DC. As illustrated in Figure 4, the AC circuit is also defined by insulated joints and require multiple sections in the track to determine direction and speed. Because of the additional rectifier component and AC power source, cost and complexity is increased (6).

Figure 4. AC Track Circuit

A design that further decreases cost and complexity is the impedance circuit, shown in Figure 5. These circuits eliminate the need for insulated joints to define the start and end of the circuit, as well as the need for multiple sections to determine speed and direction. Instead, the start and end of the circuit is defined by placing impedance bonds in between the rails, also known as Wee-Zee bonds, that serve as a transmitter and receiver for frequencies that range from 500Hz-5kHz depending on the application. When a train enters an approaching zone, its location is determined using the resulting impedance defined by the current path provided by the wheel and axle. The speed is then calculated from the rate of change in impedance (7).

Figure 5. Impedance Track Circuit

Although track circuits dominate the market for train detection in the rail industry, they still come with costly flaws. Starting from installation, the fact that it uses the rail as a means for current to travel means installing such a system requires the railroad to be put out of service and disassembled. This process alone is very costly and limiting. Another limiting factor is the availability of power utilities. Track circuits are also vulnerable to shorts resulting in false detections. Since the circuit uses the tracks directly, it is exposed to weather conditions and environmental debris. Rust and fallen objects that land across the tracks, such as tree branches or signage after severe weather, obstructs the current causing shorts or even interference resulting in false detections and/or inaccurate impedance readings. The fact that the rail is used for a current also narrows the options where they can be installed to avoid flood zones and junction areas where two or more railroads intersect. Also, for the track circuits that do use rubber inserts, they require routine maintenance to prevent the circuit from connecting to the rail outside of the approaching zone and/or damage to the rail which could cause a derailed train. The need for an off-track detection system is apparent, but none of which have been adopted by the rail industry.

3.2 Off-Track Detection Systems

The most common commercialized off-track detection system is the axle-counter. These devices use an electric field created by a transmitter and receiver placed on either side of the rail as shown in Figure 6, and the presence of a train's wheel obstructs the received transmission and makes a logic count for every instance and stores the count in memory.

Figure 6. Axle Counters

This accurately counts the number of wheels of a given train and the speed of the train is determined by the time taken between counts. The system uses an additional axle-counter on the opposite approaching zone and the track is considered occupied until the wheel count matches that of the first counter in the first zone. Although this system has proven accuracy, it is only used in the U.S. on private properties and not for grade-crossing detection systems. The main reason is the rail industry will not allow these as a standardized system for grade-crossings for the lack of a fail-safe feature. If power is lost and/or a malfunction occurs, the memory stored of the wheels counted is lost and the system will no longer be able to determine if a train is approaching or present (8).

Other off-track systems that have been researched and tested are listed in Table 1 which vary in component type and quantity.

Table 1. Researched Detection Systems

Type	Advantages/Disadvantages
Magnetometer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitors ambient magnetic field and detects unique signatures and their movement • High power and requires constant calibration (9)
GPS Sensors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracks train location and speed using network available by satellite • High cost and power with loss in satellite coverage(10)
MM-Wave Sensors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Able to detect objects within range and determine speed by calculating time difference for received signal • High power, system complexity, and false-detection rate (11)
Web Based Monitoring System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilizes video feed and processes detection on remote server, uses GPS to determine speed of train • High power consumption and dependent on network connection(12)
Laser Range Sensors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System of laser sensors that scan grade crossing and wirelessly alerts alarming device • High system complexity with need for transmitter and receiver to scan entire sectioned area, subject to false-detection's (13)
Infrared Sensors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active infrared sensors with emitting and receiving component placed on opposite sides of track, able to calculate speed with multiple pairs

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject to high amount of false detections (14)
Presence Detection Loops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cables hanging above monitored area and react to metallic presence of train • Subject to environmental damage, several false detection's (15)

Although off-track systems eliminate the high cost of installation onto the railway, they are subject to their own restrictions. The lesser powered devices are prone to false-detection's, while the higher powered devices reduce the amount of false-detection's but require availability to power utilities and/or a network connection for remote processing capabilities. Video based monitoring systems appear to have the best approach when coupled with computer vision because they have the technology to consume less power, but are subject to weather conditions and time of day. None of these systems appeal to the rail industry for the lack of fail-safe characteristics, and the commercialized axle-counters cannot be used by government transportation agencies because they require connection on rail-right-of-way which is considered private property.

4. METHODOLOGY

Thermal imaging was chosen as a method of detection because it can achieve visibility in a much wide range of environmental conditions and require less power. Field testing with an E30bx FLIR camera, illustrated in Figure 7, revealed that the wheels and axles of a train will remain above ambient temperatures due to the friction created by moving parts. The concept of the temperature difference between the wheels and ambient temperature will make the thermal signature of a train a consistent means of detection. Thermal imaging coupled with computer vision can achieve the objective of reducing the rate of false detections.

Figure 7. Top Left: Spot temp taken with FLIR camera of moving train, Top Right: Spot temperature taken of wheel, Bottom Left: Spot temp of ambient air, Bottom Right: Spot temp taken of another wheel

Thermal sensors operate as passive infrared sensors, meaning instead of emitting and receiving signals they passively react to heat radiation emitted from objects. This feature makes them extremely low power consuming and able to detect objects in various outdoor conditions with no restriction to time of the day. They are able to be used in computer vision applications by processing the temperature reading of each pixel into a color-map, whether it be a three dimensional RGB scale or single dimension for black and white images. Two separate sensors were tested that differ in resolution as well as the type of technology used for each pixel. These differences create a large gap in cost and power making them worth testing to analyze the tradeoff between cost and quality for feature extraction in order to train a stable detection model.

4.1 Convolutional Neural Networks

The method of computer vision used are convolutional neural networks (CNN). CNNs are used for training machines to classify objects using pattern recognition. It is a powerful method for computer vision to bridge the gap between human and machine decision making and has already been introduced to the rail industry with the use in wayside detectors (15). Although CNN training has many parameters that can be adjusted to achieve optimal results for different applications, the basic building blocks always follow the same fundamentals of layers as shown in Figure 8. The first layer is the convolution layer where a NxN filter, commonly called a kernel, is convoluted over the entire input image following using equation (1):

$$S(i, j) = (K * I)(i, j) = \sum_m \sum_n I(i - m, j - n)K(m, n) \quad (1)$$

where S is the resulting two dimensional array of (i, j) ; I = input image as a two dimensional array of (m, n) ; and K = NxN filter array.

Figure 8. Fundamental Building Blocks of a Convolutional Neural Network

The size and quantity of kernels vary depending on the application but the values they contain extract features from the image that are used to recognize specific patterns for an object of interest. The following pooling layer is used to reduce the size of the convoluted feature map in order to decrease computation during processing which allows for models to run on smaller devices such as the one used for this project. Finally, the last block consists of the fully connected layers which transforms the two dimensional arrays into a single dimension and appends them together. The dimensions of each connected layer reduces to funnel the parameters down in size to prepare for the final layer where classification is performed. The dimensions of the final layer are equal to the number of classifications the model is trained to predict which, in this application are two for images with a train and images with no train. With the exception of pooling layers, each layer contains an activation function which is used to activate nodes which features relevant patterns. During training, each output of the classification layer measures how far off it is from its actual classification, or label, using a loss function and the weights and biases are updated accordingly through backward propagation to fit the model. Therefore, a model performing poorly is considered as overfitting or underfitting (17).

4.2 MLX Sensor

The first sensor tested was the Melexis MLX90640, shown in Figure 9. The MLX sensor uses a 24x32 array of thermopile capacitors to read ambient temperatures. The field of view (FOV) for the particular sensor used is 110°x55° and the frame rate can operate between 5Hz-64Hz while using less than 115mW of power (18). The MLX is commonly used for indoor applications and has achieved great results for object detection using machine learning algorithms (19). The biggest challenge with using the MLX for an outdoor application would be the heat absorbed by ground and static objects causing them to dominate the image.

Figure 9. MLX90640 Thermopile Array Sensor

The MLX requires only four pins for operation; the SDA and SCL for serial communication via I2C, a 3.3V-5V power, and ground pin. The pin connections are as follows:

- SDA -> GPIO 2
- SCL -> GPIO 3
- Vcc -> BOARD 1
- GND -> BOARD 9

The program to run the MLX was forked from the (20) github repository. Github is an open source website that supports software development by providing all necessary programs uploaded by manufacturers and other developers. From the files obtained, the C++ file named rawrgb was utilized and called within a Python script to collect images. The rawrgb script reads the temperature of all the pixels and fills them into a color-mapped array which is streamed as an output. The color map is scaled from 0-255, zero being black which represents the coldest possible value and 255 being white which represents the hottest. The python script captures the output in chunks of 2304 bytes and displays them as an image using Python Imaging Library (PILLOW). In order to collect images for training data, the python script was written to save two images every second until a set max number is reached. The system setup is shown in Figure 10 which consists of the MLX attached to the Raspberry Pi mounted on a tripod, a 7 inch monitor to navigate directories and display images, and a 26800mAh power supply.

Figure 10. Mobile Setup for Testing

The area chosen for collecting data was next to a Union Pacific Rail Yard located off S New Braunfels Ave and Duval St. near downtown San Antonio, TX. The module was placed on Duval St., which is a public road, in order to insure that the device was outside of the rail right-of-way while still attempting to keep the sensor at a close enough range to eliminate any unnecessary heat in the FOV from dominating the thermal image. The tripod was positioned 25' from the active railroad and raised for the sensor to be 2'4" at $\sim 15^\circ$ - 20° angle from ground level as shown in Figure 11. From the figure, it can also be seen that the images were collected on a day with clear skies. The time was approximately 11 am and the outside temperature ranged from 83° to 87° Fahrenheit during the time spent waiting for a train to pass.

Figure 11. Area for collecting data with MLX90640

Although the resolution of the MLX was too low to determine the temperature difference from the wheels of the train as intended, the shape of the train was clearly defined as shown in Figure 12. The pictures on the left were taken of the track for comparison while the MLX was collecting images when a train was present and when the track was vacant. It can be seen that the thermal

image of a train does not offer many features that can be extracted to train a CNN model, although there is a clear difference between the thermal images with and without a train present. The thermal signature that defines the train is created by the absorbed heat from the sun, as well as the heat signature of the ballast which is the hottest point of the image and represented as a magenta color, closest on the color scale to white. A total of 3400 images were collected, 1700 of a train present and 1700 of no train present, and arranged in appropriate directories to begin training a CNN model. Preparation for training begins first with gathering images to use as input data and then

Figure 12. Images taken of track with and without train compared to thermal images taken with MLX90640

processing the arrangement of images into appropriate directories to signify which class, or label, they belong to. For this project, the two classifications are positive for images with a train present,

and negative for images with no train. Next, the complete dataset is split into three sub-directories for training, validation, and test sets with a 80/10/10 ratio, respectively. The training set of images are used for training the model and the validation set is used to evaluate the model performance during training and provide feedback for tuning the model's parameters. Because the model will continuously use the training and validation sets throughout the training process, inevitably a bias will occur on particular features found in images and cause overfitting during training. To properly evaluate the model after training has finished, the test set of images are used to evaluate the performance on new, unbiased images that have not been introduced in the training process.

Before the process of training begins, an analysis of the images was performed using Canny Edge Detection to determine the best approach to constructing the model architecture. Canny is one of the most common feature extraction filters for edge detection, which is a powerful tool used for pattern recognition in computer vision (21). The Canny algorithm uses the Gaussian function for the two-dimensional images and then calculates the gradient vector following equations (2) and (3).

$$G(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2} e^{-\frac{x^2+y^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla G(x, y, \sigma) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial G}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial G}{\partial y} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where:

G is a two dimensional array of (x,y); σ is the Gaussian notation for standard distribution; and ∂ is the notation for partial derivative.

Then, the dot product of the gradient is taken with respect to both x and y using equations (4) and (5) respectively. Finally, the magnitude and angle are found with equations (6) and (7) (21).

$$P_x = \frac{\partial G(x, y, \sigma)}{\partial x} \cdot G(x, y) \quad (4)$$

$$P_y = \frac{\partial G(x, y, \sigma)}{\partial y} \cdot G(x, y) \quad (5)$$

$$|P| = \sqrt{P_x^2 + P_y^2} \quad (6)$$

$$(\theta) = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{P_y}{P_x}\right) \quad (7)$$

where P is the product of the dot product; G is the two dimensional Gaussian of (x,y) ; $|P|$ is the magnitude of P ; and θ is the vector angle of P .

Canny edge detection was then performed on the images taken with the MLX containing a train and images of no train as shown in Figure 13. The results show how much noise is present among the temperature values represented by each pixel. The images displaying the edge detection algorithm are not distinguishable between the image containing a train and the one without which would make pattern recognition impossible for training. To counter this, an image processing technique was used that creates a threshold for black and white images. Since the values for each pixel are represented by an RGB colormap on the scale of 0-255, converting the images into a binary colormap would change the pixel color to either black or white depending if the pixel value crossed a specified threshold. All the images containing a train were evaluated at various threshold to determine an optimized value. This was necessary because every car on the train is different and therefore absorbed heat at different rates. The value chosen gave results displayed in Figure 14.

Figure 13. Canny Edge Detection Performed on MLX Thermal Image

Figure 14. Canny Edge Detection Performed on Binary Thresholding Image

By using a binary threshold, the noise in the image was greatly reduced making the pattern of a train visible for the edge detection algorithm. This made CNN training achievable but still presented a challenging task. The threshold chosen is a single constant value and since the various cars of a passing train absorb heat at different rates, the pattern of a train is not consistent for all train cars as shown in Figure 15. These images all contain a train and yet some are not visible due to the varying heat absorption at different angles. Still, a pattern containing a larger sum of black pixels can differentiate when a train is indeed present and will be tested to determine if it is enough to train a detection model. The model was trained in python language using Keras API. Keras is a popular open source library used for training various types of artificial neural networks. The first model attempted used a flattened input. This means that the two-dimensional image of 32x24 was converted into a single array with 768 values. Since the canny edge detection produced an image that was similar in features compared to the image with a binary threshold, there was a high

Figure 15. Thermal images with varying temperatures of train shown with binary threshold

probability that the model would detect patterns without the need of performing convolution to extract additional features. The connected layers obtained a total of three dense layers for the fully connected block. The final dense layer contains two neurons for the positive and negative classifications and uses softmax activation function to determine the probability of the two. The softmax activation is most commonly used for the final classification layer and follows equation (8).

$$\text{softmax}(x)_i = \frac{\exp(x_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^n \exp(x_j)} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Relu } g(z) = \max(0, z) \quad (9)$$

where x_i is the input vector; x_j is the output vector; and n is the number of possible classification. The two preceding dense layers were set to 460 and 230 neurons, respectively, and both used the rectified linear unit (Relu) activation function which follows Equation (9). Relu is the commonly used activation function in neural networks because it normalized all the negative values as zero, resulting in faster computation speed and better performance. For that reason, more channels are used to counter the loss of information (22). The reason for adding additional dense layers to help narrow down the array size before the final layer is to lessen the computation per neuron which increases efficiency and accuracy (23). The model was compiled using binary-crossentropy loss for 30 epochs and performed with an accuracy displayed in Figure 16.

Accuracy graphs display the performance of training by recording the error calculated of the difference between the predicted output and the expected output of each epoch in a range from 0 to 1 (23). The error is plotted for both the training set and the validation set, which are shown as blue and orange. An ideal model performance should begin with a low training accuracy and increase in an exponential manner with the validation accuracy following below it with the same

Figure 16. Accuracy during Training of Flattened Model trained for 30 epochs

pattern. The performance of training accuracy for this model behaves in an unexpected manner. Both the training and the validation sets begin close to 100 percent and the validation drops radically throughout the entire 30 epochs which is a clear sign of overfitting. This is validated by the confusion matrix in Figure 17. The confusion matrix displays the models predictions of each image within the test set in an NxN array, where N is the number of classifications. It categorizes the predictions made according to the labeled directories which are negative and positive. The number of positive classifications the model predicted correctly are considered as true positives (TP), and the number of positive classifications the model predicts incorrectly are considered as false positives (FP). The total accuracy of the model is determined by summing the amount of TP and FP and then dividing by the entire test set using equation (10). A total accuracy of 49% was determined using the flattened model.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + FP}{TP + FP + FN + TN} \quad (10)$$

```
Confusion Matrix, without normalization
[[ 86 114]
 [ 89 111]]
```


Figure 17. Confusion Matrix for Flattened Model

The next model architecture used the same connected layers with a single convolution layer obtaining 8 kernels with 3x3 dimensions. This model used the same loss function for binary classification but trained for 50 epochs. The performance of the model exemplified an exponential increase after approximately 15 epochs as shown in Figure 18. Even so, the sporadic drops in the validation curve show signs of overfitting with large drops occurring early in training and smaller drops further into training.

Figure 18. Accuracy during Training of Model with Single Convolution

The confusion matrix for the second model, Figure 19, again validates overfitting just as the first. The addition of the convolution layer did help achieve a better accuracy of 53%, but nothing that would be acceptable for implementation.

Figure 19. Confusion Matrix of Model with Single Convolution

As a result, the binary images were further analyzed to determine an appropriate threshold of black pixels which would indicate a train's presence. A program was written to sum the number of black pixels for each image in two separate directories, one for images with a train and one for images with no train, both containing one thousand. The binary threshold which created the black and white images from the RGB images by the MLX was set to 145 on a 0-255 scale. The images with no train were observed to have a maximum count of black pixels reach 236. For the images containing a train, the lowest summation of black pixels was 288. A model was created with a hard coded threshold of 250 to determine a train's presence for testing.

4.3 Flir Lepton Sensor

The second sensor tested was the FLIR Lepton 3.0 displayed in Figure 20. The technology of the Lepton differed from the MLX allowing it to have a much higher resolution which created thermal images rich in features. The pixels of the Lepton use an uncooled microbolometer technology

Figure 20. LIR Lepton 3.0 Thermal Camera on V2 Breakout Board

which enables the size of each to be much smaller and sensitive to long-wave infrared light in the spectrum of $8\mu\text{m}$ to $14\mu\text{m}$, enabling it to see further (24). The resolution of the Lepton is 160×120 with a FOV of 57° horizontal and 71° vertical and a frame rate of 8.7 Hz. One drawback of this technology is the need for periodic calibration. FLIR offers an automatic flat field correction (FFC) within the embedded system as well as a mechanical shutter which can be seen as the black square shape surrounding the camera lens. An FFC event will occur at periodic intervals and when the ambient temperature changes. During which, the use of the shutter will spike power consumption from an operating level of 150 mW to 650 mW for roughly a tenth of a second. Connection to the Raspberry Pi required I2C communication just as the MLX, but in addition requires the use of a SPI bus as well for streaming the video feed. Pin selection to the Raspberry Pi is as follows:

- CS -> GPIO 8
- CLK -> GPIO 11
- SCL -> GPIO 3
- SDA -> GPIO 2
- MISO -> GPIO 9
- VSYNC -> GPIO 17

The program to run the Lepton was forked from the (25) repository. The raspberrypi_video program, found within the software directory, was utilized to stream video feed. The folder contains several threads that run in parallel and use the QT library written in C++. QT is a programming application that generates code in C++ specifically for running multiple scripts simultaneously without interference. Modifications had to be made to the program to enable frame capturing from the video feed to be used for collecting data for training purposes. The Lepton-Thread and main scripts were modified to enable frames to be saved at the click of a button that was placed within the widget displaying the video feed. The images collected from the Lepton offer much more details in defining features for object detection as shown in Figure 21. The file that runs the Lepton allows for the video to run in three different color-modes named grayscale, ironblack, and rainbow. The images in Figure 21 were taken in ironblack, which is the default, and the rainbow color mode created images much like the RGB colormap created with the MLX images. The problem with using ironblack color mode was presented when the engine car of a train passes which produces the most heat from the exhaust on top. This would cause the image to focus only on the hottest point and everything else in the image fade to almost black. Using the

Figure 21. Test images taken with Lepton 3.0 to analyze the quality of resolution

grayscale color-mode reacted better to this situation than the other two and therefore used afterward. The area chosen for collecting data this time was approximately one mile east from the Union Pacific Kirby Yard in San Antonio, TX. This area provided enough space to capture images at different angles and distances from the track as shown in Figure 22. Having images taken at multiple angles provided a variation of features for pattern recognition. One factor that played an important role was whether the sun was directly behind or in front of the camera, as the two top photos illustrate. Another factor that needed attention was the objects captured in the background. The bottom photo shows the top of a building captured in the frame. Details such as this influence what patterns help contribute to classification during training. A total of 1200 frames were collected of various train cars from the same location at different times of the day and analyzed using the same canny edge detection algorithm to verify definable features. Figure 23 displays in the first column a lepton image capturing a train passing at day between the hours of 10am-11am

Figure 22. Illustration of various angles available to collect data at Kirby location

with an outdoor temperature of 89° - 20° and a corresponding image below of the vacant track. The third column displays a train passing before the sun rose between the hours of 5am-6am with an outdoor temperature of 74° - 20° and an image below of the vacant track at the same time and temperature. The images in column two and four illustrate the canny edge detection algorithm verifying that the thermal images offer consistent pattern recognition for train detection at night and day. Since the thermal images taken with the Lepton provided sufficient feature details, training a model for the Flir was taken in a different approach. There are two types of object detection methods commonly used with image processing. The first is a standard classification when the model runs an inference and predicts if the entire image is classified as a particular label.

Figure 23. Canny edge detection applied to lepton images with/without train at day and nighttime

This type was tested for the MLX model. The second detection is called single-shot detector (SSD) which is able to predict the coordinates within the frame containing the detected object with bounding boxes. The benefit of using SSD is the ability to detect multiple objects within a 'single shot.' The term single shot refers to the model's ability to classify an object and its location with the use of two loss functions in single forward pass for the confidence of the object's classification and the object's location (26). SSD models are pre-configured architectures that are available as open source. These established architectures can be found on Tensorflow's github repository as pre-trained models with weights already established using popular online image data-sets such as ImageNet, COCO, and Google's Open Image. These sets contain the same hierarchy discussed in the preparation for training the MLX model but contain ten to hundred thousand of images with a 100+ classifications. Although, the images in these data-sets are taken from standard video and picture cameras and the weights associated with the pre-trained models are trained for exactly these. This makes the model's weights not perform nearly as well on images generated from

different types of sensors such as the thermal images from the MLX and Lepton. However, the architecture of these deep network models can still provide better performance in speed and accuracy and are available to train on custom datasets through a process called transfer learning (27).

The architecture chosen for the Lepton detection model was SSd MobileNet V1 (28). The MobileNet V1 model is popular because it offers high accuracy at fast speeds that are ideal for real time applications. MobileNet V1 is known for its architecture containing two trademark designs called depthwise separable and pointwise convolutions. These designs focus on minimizing the size and number of kernels in each layer which impacts the computational cost with a reduction of 1/9 compared to a standard convolution (27). The reduction in computation results in faster processing with less memory enabling compact and mobile device applications. Although training the model is still computationally demanding due to the repetitive feed forward and backward calculations in obtaining the model weights and is recommended on larger machines.

Training was done locally on a PC equipped with a graphics unit processor (GPU). Using a GPU allows training speed to be substantially faster because they are designed to perform large matrix computations to provide a faster frame per second to be displayed on high resolution computer screens. Integration with deep neural networks and GPUs was made available by NVIDIA, a GPU manufacturer, through CUDA-toolkit and CUDA-Deep-Neural-Network (cuDNN) open source libraries (29). Because technology is constantly advancing and library versions are updated regularly, caution has to be taken on what versions are used in order to ensure compatibility. To train the SSD model, Tensorflow's open source Object Detection Application Programming Interface (API) was used. This program contains all the necessary codes and pre-trained models, such as MobileNet, to successfully train an object detection model with various model

architectures. To prepare images for training, instead of separating images into sub-directories for labeling the API program requires actual labeling of images with bounding boxes. This process was done using another open source program called LabelImg that is available on the PIP repository, which is an online package installation for python. For each image, LabelImg saves an eXtensible Markup Language (XML) file that contains the coordinates of the object of interest. The XML file is then used to create an additional comma-separated-value (CSV) file that the Object Detection API reads to locate and classify the object or objects. After the files are made, the images are then split into training and test directories. Unlike the classification training approach, the test directory is used as the validation set for the loss function to calculate the error. All that is needed after arranging the images and files in the appropriate directories is running the train python script that is provided in the API package. During training, checkpoints are saved in .ckpt files and are used to evaluate performance with the Tensorboard application that is also provided by Tensorflow. Tensorboard uses the summation of the confidence and location loss function results as a means of measurement, as seen in Figure 24. The graph shows the model was trained for 80k steps, which is the number of iterations the model updated the weights during training, which took approximately one hour of training.

Figure 24. Performance of MobileNet v1 model during training

The darker line is the averaged loss and the faded is the actual loss at the time per each check point. Training was ended at 80k steps because the loss function began to settle out at a ratio of 2 whereas the weights of the model would no longer be updated. Before transferring the trained model onto the Raspberry Pi, the accuracy was tested by simulating the performance on images that the model had not seen during training. Figure 25 illustrates the model also suffered overfitting by producing multiple detections on several locations of the image. Prediction ran twice on the same image with very different results. The first image resulted with a bounding box around the train but also several boxes overlapping as if to signify there is multiple trains in the image. The second inference failed to detect the train all together and once again produced multiple bounding boxes overlapping one another. This was a clear sign that model has a problem with differentiating feature patterns that define a train. To narrow down whether the problem was due to the type of model architecture chosen, several others were trained with the same dataset as illustrated by Figure 26.

Figure 25. Detection images exemplifying overfitting

The additional models chosen to train included the second version of MobileNet, the MobileNet v2 model, and their quantized versions. MobileNet v2 features a signature architecture using inverted residuals and linear bottleneck, which together help further decrease computation and loss information (30). Their quantized version takes another approach at achieving faster computation by compressing the bit size of the program instead of architecture design (31). Each of the MobileNet models trained for roughly an hour but the most efficient was the MobileNet v2 model

which achieved a loss ratio of 1.2. The quantized MobileNet v2 model booted out of training at the first check point due to compatibility issues with Tensorflow version that was used. An evaluation of the v2's accuracy was done by performing an inference on several test images the model had not yet seen. The results shown in Figure 27 illustrate that model had yet not learned to differentiate defining features of the object it was trained to detect. The first image contains a train and the model performed well with 99% probability that it is a train. The other two images were of a person and a doorway which the model still predicted a high probability that they were a train as well. This would result in several false detections on a real time application and would therefore not serve as adequate model.

Figure 26. Performance of multiple models trained

Figure 27. Inference made with MobileNet v2 model on several test images

The next attempt to train a model went back to the classification method that was used for the images collected by the MLX sensor. The obstacle with training an SSD model to detect trains

was including non-train objects in the image for the model to learn in order to classify other feature patterns that it will encounter in real time. Since a train is a large and continuous object, it fills the entire image and thus does not allow for the model to learn what is not a train. Using the classification approach allows this theory to be tested in a non-time consuming manner by arranging images of trains and images not containing a train into their appropriate sub-directory instead of labeling each image.

Keras was used again for transfer learning on the MobileNet v1 model. The v1 model was chosen because the architecture of the last pooling layer was designed to be a single dimension as shown in Figure 28. The last layer has a total of 1000 outputs to classify that many objects. For this application only two is needed, train and no train, and would require eliminating the final layer of the v1 model and applying instead a layer with only two outputs. The mentioned pooling layer also allowed four additional layers to be eliminated to help further reduce the model size and computation. The parameters were reduced from 4,253,864 to 3,230,914, as shown in Figure 29 which significantly reduces the memory and processing.

conv_pw_13_relu (ReLU)	(None, 7, 7, 1024)	0
global_average_pooling2d (G1	(None, 1024)	0
reshape_1 (Reshape)	(None, 1, 1, 1024)	0
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 1, 1, 1024)	0
conv_preds (Conv2D)	(None, 1, 1, 1000)	1025000
reshape_2 (Reshape)	(None, 1000)	0
act_softmax (Activation)	(None, 1000)	0
=====		
Total params: 4,253,864		
Trainable params: 4,231,976		
Non-trainable params: 21,888		

Figure 28. Parameters of MobileNet V1 architecture

The same 1200 images taken by the Kirby rail-yard were used and an additional 80 images were taken of the vacant track at the same location with and without background objects. An additional 20 more images were taken of the cars passing on the grade-crossing. To further increase the dataset, data augmentation was implemented to alter the images by rotating them at various angles and adjusting the brightness to create new images for training. After, a total of 170 images were arranged as the validation set and the same amount for the test set. The weights of the first 23 layers of the MobileNet v1 model were set as an initial value for training and then trained for 10 epochs. Freezing the weights in a specified number of layers allows the new model to advantage of the pre-trained bias to help influence the bias of the layers that will trained on the custom dataset. The validation accuracy hit 100% during training for only 10 epochs, which closely relates to

conv_pw_13_relu (ReLU)	(None, 7, 7, 1024)	0
global_average_pooling2d (Gl	(None, 1024)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 2)	2050
=====		
Total params: 3,230,914		
Trainable params: 1,865,730		
Non-trainable params: 1,365,184		

Figure 29. Parameters of modified MobileNet architecture

overfitting, but the model was evaluated on the test set and analyzed using a confusion matrix shown in Figure 30. With 0 being the label for non-train images and 1 the label for images with a train, the model misclassified only one image from both labels. This model reached an accuracy of 98% and was used for further testing. The models performance would still need to be analyzed in real time for different environments in which the dataset was taken. Since the test set of images were taken in the same area as the training set, it is common for a detection model to perform well. The model was exported as a protobuf file, or pb file which is the standard file for Tensorflow to

read a model architecture and associated weights, and implemented on the Raspberry Pi. Once it was implemented on the Raspberry, a test run was used to determine the approximate time for a prediction to be processed on a single image. Because an image varies in pixel values, the prediction process will vary accordingly. An average of 100 frames were taken and approximated to 0.420 seconds. The program for running the video stream was modified to run an additional thread in parallel that would save a frame every .420 seconds and used as an input tensor for the detection algorithm.

Figure 30. Confusion matrix of model created using transfer learning. Accuracy of 98%

4.4 Development of Network Communication

This section describes the implementation of wireless communication. The modules communicate to one another locally using radio frequency with each consisting of their own unique pipeline address. A single detection module communicates a signal to a warning device when to flash a beacon after the speed has been determined and a CWT has been calculated. At

the time a detection occurs, the time, date, and speed is logged and transmitted to an online server when a network is available. The online server then updates a mobile application to provide further preemptive warning to motorists in addition to flashing a warning beacon at the grade crossing.

4.4.1 Wireless Communication

The nRF24L01 is single chip radio transceiver that operates in the 2.4GHz ISM bandwidth, making transmission range reach up to 100 meters with minimal obstructions. The frequency channels, communication protocol setup, and the desired output power can be adjusted and programmed using the SPI interface. Power consumption can reach as low as 9 mA at -6 dBm output settings and require approximately 12 mA during receiving (32). The nRF24 modules use the Nordic semiconductor and offer up to six communication pipelines as illustrated in Figure 31. One of the pipe addresses is dedicated for writing, but the other five are available for listening. This gives the option of up to five different devices in a system with individual addresses allocated for receiving transmission, making each one read and write capable and fit into a star network topology.

Figure 31. Illustration of multiple pipelines achieved with nRF24L01

One of the benefits achieved with a star network that our project would feature is the ability for all the nodes to communicate only to a single master node. Also, a star network has the flexibility for one module to malfunction and the remaining modules still able to function and communicate properly (33). The nRF24L01 modules also feature acknowledgement payload functions within the libraries. Using ACK functions help ensure successful transmission of packets. A capacitor between the V_{cc} and GND pins on each nRF module was implemented to prevent the power supply to the nRF modules from varying slightly which results in restricting proper functionality.

The python library to run communication using the nRF module was provided by (34). A modification to the SPI speed had to be made on the config file that increased the frequency to 4MHz. After which, communication between devices was achieved. Also, an additional SPI bus had to be enabled on the Raspberry to allow constant communication for the Lepton video stream and sporadic communication for the nRF while sending signals. After enabling interface with the second SPI bus and disabling Bluetooth capabilities, because by default Bluetooth occupies the additional SPI bus, it was found that the communication speed was drastically reduced. This was apparent when the video stream of the Lepton began to refresh approximately 5-8 seconds after opening up the second SPI bus. To resolve this, an additional Raspberry was used in conjunction with the Raspberry interfacing with the Lepton and programmed to send a signal to the warning module when a GPIO pin was turned HIGH which indicates when a train is detected. The pin would remain high until three consecutive frames are classified as no train. The requirement of three frames help reduce hast assumptions that the train has passed if a frame is classified incorrectly while a train is in motion.

4.4.2 Mobile Application

The cloud server application will use Firebase API to send and receive data from the system. Firebase is a development tool designed by Google for creating web and mobile applications. This API allows for basic security functions in the form of individual tokens and access keys for the web application and to a device. The Raspberry Pi will be using a REST-ful web socket to connect and send data to the Firebase cloud using the following communication protocols: link layer: 4G/LTE mobile network, Network layer: IPV4, Transport: TCP, Application: HTTP. The mobile application used for testing the system will be created using android studio and coded in Java language. For the system to connect to firebase, the python-firebase package was used. This package makes use of requests library and lets data be transferred between the online firebase database and the Raspberry Pi. In the Firebase account, the Realtime database gives the ability to set up security and provides the web address to send and download data from the database. For this application we are only sending data of each detection to the database. The data that is collected is the date, time, and speed of the train for each detection. This data is saved in two locations on the Raspberry Pi. One is the full detection data log of all detection's and the second containing data that has not been sent to Firebase database. When there is internet connection, the link between Firebase Realtime Database and the Raspberry Pi 4 is made and the data is transferred. After all the data is transferred, the second log is deleted. This is done to save the time it takes to send data to the Firebase Database. The logged data can be seen in Figure 32. Once the data is transferred to the real-time database it is then accessible using the created mobile application. The application was created in Android Studio, which Firebase is optimized to work with. By linking the Firebase account to the Android Studio project, the information on the real-time database is displayed showing the same information sent to the cloud (date, time, and speed of each detection). With this data the system can be monitored to verify proper operation and

compare the data collected to the train schedule. The application has two main windows. The first is the home screen of the application and the second is where the data is displayed in Figure 33. This creates a simple interface for the user to see the data and the ability to see the data collected on the online Firebase account.

Figure 32. Detection data displayed in Firebase Realtime Database

Figure 33. Mobile Application Design that displays logged information of train detections

5. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

5.1 Communication Testing

A small-scale experimental setup was built as a proof of concept. Communication amongst devices and the mobile application was first verified using one warning module and two detection modules. The detection modules were placed at a specified distance from one another as shown in Figure 34. When the first detection is triggered, a time stamp is used as a reference to calculate the difference in time from the second detection and divided by the specified distance, which was referenced in feet for testing, to determine the speed. Then, the second module is tasked with

Figure 34. Communication test illustrating specified distance of detection modules to calculate speed from time difference of two detections

signaling the warning module to flash after an appropriate delay to resemble a standardized CWT and upload information to the online server. The flow of functionality and which device provides the appropriate signal is illustrated in Figure 35. Communication was consistent throughout several

test runs for determining the speed of a person walking past the modules. The online server was also successful in updating the mobile application immediately after the second detection occurs.

Figure 35. Flow of communication amongst devices, blue represents RF signal and yellow mobile network connection

5.2 Field Testing of Thermal Detection

The field test infrastructure is made to easily move, change direction, or height depending on the testing location and is made to be completely disassembled to allow for the moving to different test locations. The solar panel mount was set at a fix location of 26 degrees and is positioned to the south to allow for the maximum amount of power to be absorbed by the panel. The angle was set at the winter angle to allow for the maximum amount of energy to be collected during the winter months. It was set for the winter months because this is when the least amount of sun is available and excess energy will be generated during the summer. A 1.22 m (4 ft.) by 1.22 m (4 ft.) base was fabricated by cutting and welding 5.08 cm (2-inch) square tubing to support the weight of the structure and prevent the structure from falling over in high winds. A 3.05 m (10 ft.) section of 12 gage steel channels was used to mount the components onto the structure since the holes in the channel allow for components to easily be altered for prototyping/ field test. A 3.05 m (10 ft.) section of the channel is used due to it being the maximum size height to fit in the lab. On the structure representing the stop ahead sign, the detection module is mounted at a height of 0.61 m (2 ft.) above the ground and the solar panel is mounted at the top of the pole to prevent the solar panel from being tampered with. On the stop sign structure, the sign is mounted 2.13 m (7 ft.)

above the ground on the test pole, the warning module receiving unit is mounted behind the stop sign, the beacon is mounted on the top of the pole, and the solar panel is mounted between the stop sign and the beacon. The warning module receiving unit is positioned behind the stop sign to hide the unit from view to reduce the possibility of theft. The beacon is positioned 0.30 m (1 ft.) from the top of the stop.

Figure 36. Warning Network Field Test Structure

The components described in the methodology section for both detection and warning modules are all connected on a single PCB Board and then attached to the plastic system housing. The power converter is connected to the housing with bolts and the battery is connected to the housing with 10 lb. industrial Velcro to allow the battery to be easily removed for testing. The wires for the system are all connected with quick connects to allow the system to be connected and disconnected easily.

Figure 37. Detection Module

Figure 38. Warning Module

Most of the testing for the thermal detection model was done at the same location where the images were collected near the Kirby railyard and the performance was evaluated at several distances from the active railway track. For every instance that a train passed, the model succeeded in classifying at least a single frame as a detection. However, whether the model consistently classified each frame while a train was passing was dependent on several factors. The first was how far the device was placed from the active railway. At a distance of approximately 50ft, the model achieved the highest efficiency of performance in terms of consistent classifications. When the device was placed approximately 25ft from the active railway, the consistency of accurate classifications reduced when the train was traveling at faster speeds. Figure 39 captures the screen during testing while the video stream from the Lepton is shown in the window named raspberrypi video, the input image of the detection algorithm with the predicted class written in red, and two command terminals. The top right terminal displays the predicted class along with a counter that increments with every detection and the time elapsed between predictions. These variables were printed for debugging purposes but also revealed that the timing for each prediction is not consistent.

Figure 39. Screen captured displaying test results at 25ft from the active railway when train stopped

Normally the timing would range between 0.350s-0.550s, but when other operations were performed such as screen recording the latency would increase. The observation in the image was documented while the device was placed 25ft from the track while a train was slowing to a stop and then reversing. During the entire observation, the detection module classified each frame correctly the entire time. Other times at the same distance, the consistency in correct classifications reduced when a train was traveling at faster speeds. This resulted in distorted images produced by the Lepton such as the one in Figure 40. The distortion in the image signifies the refresh rate of the Lepton camera cannot capture an object traveling at a higher speed when placed at this distance. The distortion resulted in an inconsistency for the detection model to classify the frame using pattern recognition. At distances of approximately 70ft and above, the performance was greatly reduced with at times only classifying the engine car of the train correctly and the rest as misclassifications. Another observation was made when objects were in front of the train, such as

Figure 40. Distorted image created by Lepton as a result of train traveling at fast speed

a light post or telephone pole, that were foreign to the training set of images caused the module to misclassify frames while a train was passing. Such an instance is captured in Figure 41.

Figure 41. Electrical pole causing detection model to misclassify frame as train was passing

The camera was angled in such a way to capture an electrical pole placed before the track. When a train was passing the model predicted several misclassifications until the camera was repositioned at an angle that did not capture the pole, at which the model started to accurately classify frames as a train detection. When situations like these occurred, images were saved and

the model was retrained with the additional data to achieve better performance. Similar results occurred when testing was performed in new environments. If objects in the FOV were foreign to the training set of images, such as buildings or fences, the model would perform inefficiently until additional training was done with images containing the new objects. It was also observed that trains in different areas contain different types of cars. For example, trains traveling to Houston, TX have a different consistency in freight compared to trains traveling to Del Rio, TX. Therefore, additional images were needed to train the model for different routes. Figure 42 displays an image of a correctly classified frame in a different environment from where the original training data was collected. This was the result of collecting additional images in new environment and retraining the detection model. The image to the right of the classified frame captures the test setup with an additional Raspberry Pi equipped with two 5V LEDs (circled in red) flashing after the Raspberry Pi equipped with the Lepton transmitted an RF signal signifying a detection.

Figure 42. Testing of RF transmission when train detection occurs

5.3 Cost and Power Analysis

The estimated cost for a single detection system is shown in Table 2. The total includes prices of components used for testing and an estimated cost for a weather sealed housing, which was

determined from several searches of a camera housing for commercialized FLIR camera systems, as well as an estimated cost of electrical components for wiring and charging the device. The estimated cost for a single warning device is shown in Table 3. This cost includes a MCU with less processing power, since it will be used only to receive a RF signal and serve as a switch to flash a beacon, an RF module, price of 12V beacon and housing, and costs of electrical components needed to power and charge the system.

Table 2. Estimated Cost for Detection Device

Component	Cost
Raspberry Pi 4	\$55
Flir Lepton 3.0	\$248.99
MLX90640	\$58.50
RF module	\$3.00
Estimated Detection Housing	\$300.00
Power Source and Other Electrical Components	\$100.00
Total	\$765.49

Table 3. Estimated Cost for Warning Device

Component	Cost
Microcontroller	\$5.00
RF Module	\$3.00
Beacon with Housing	\$130.00

Component	Cost
Power Source and Other Electrical Components	\$100.00
Total	\$238.00

The total estimated cost for developing the entire proposed system consisting of four detection devices and two warning devices would be $(4 \times 765.49) + (2 \times 238.00) = \$3,537.96$, which is less expensive than a standard track circuit system.

Power consumption was observed and recorded during several processing events as shown in Table 4. Since each component has a constant power rating, an accurate measurement of the entire system power consumption had to be determined while processing each algorithm and measuring power between the Raspberry Pi and the power source. The Raspberry Pi consumes 2.65W at idle. Running the MLX along with the binary summation algorithm increases the power consumption by 430mW. Streaming video from the Lepton without running the neural network program increases power consumption by 370mW. While running the video and detection algorithm, power consumption increases by 2.07W. This illustrates how much processing a machine learning algorithm can influence system power ratings. The power is also influenced by the need for the Lepton to perform an ffc function for calibration. When this occurs, the mechanical shutter closes for less than a second but spikes power consumption an additional 2.76W. Having a weather sealed housing that will keep temperatures consistent will minimize how often a ffc function occurs since it is caused by change in ambient temperature.

Table 4. Power Consumption

Processing	Voltage	Amperage	Power
In Idle	5.15V	0.52A	2.68W
Running MLX90640 w/binary thres.	5.15V	0.59A	3.08W
Steaming Lepton Video	5.15V	0.58A	2.99W
Running DNN Algorithm	5.15V	0.90A	4.63W
Running DNN and ffc	5.15V	1.03A	5.30W

With the present operations, the estimated watts per hour would be a consistent 4.63Wh to run the Lepton camera along with the detection algorithm. An appropriate battery size would have to provide at minimum 22Ah for a single day. If an operation were added to save power, such as an interrupt to wake the detection from a sleep mode, it would significantly reduce power consumption. One such design was considered using the MLX binary threshold algorithm as a primary detection to trigger the CNN detection model to turn on. The MLX processing consumes on average 3.08Wh. If a train is assumed to occupy the track for an estimated fifteen minutes that will reduce the amount of time the CNN model will be running to an average of 1.18Wh for every train passing. Table 5 illustrates the required Amps/hour per day for a number of assumed trains passing in a single day using Equation (11).

$$Ah = \frac{(24 - N)(i) + N(j)}{V} \quad (11)$$

where Ah is amperage per hour; N is the number of trains passes in a day, i is the power consumed by MLX detection in watts/hour and j is the power consumed by Lepton detection in watts/hour.

Table 5. Estimated Power Consumption using Sleep Mode

Number of Trains/day	Amperage Required/day
5	15.50Ah
4	15.27Ah
3	15.04Ah
2	14.81Ah
1	14.58Ah

Using a sleep mode for running the Lepton detection algorithm will decrease the daily power used by 27%. Implementing such an operation will reduce the required size of a battery which would result in lower cost of development.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the development of a thermal train detection model was successful using computer vision and CNN algorithms. The model achieved a high accuracy with set conditions, such as distance from the tracks and objects in the back or foreground that were not featured in the training data and foreign to the model. Wireless communication amongst devices was also achieved using RF transmission and the speed of a moving object of interest was confirmed with the use of two detection devices placed at a set distance apart from one another and CWT was calculated. In addition, further preemptive warning was also established using an online server and mobile application. The cost and power of the system was determined and compared with existing technology. Progress and testing of the project was limited due to the nature of train scheduling. For future work, more real time testing would need to be performed with both the MLX and Lepton for further evaluation and comparison. Also, additional data needs to be collected to train the detection model to reduce the chances of foreign objects and environments. Strongly suggested that images from a wide variety of environments are collected for training to reduce the number of unknown objects to the model. A weather sealed containment box would have to be obtained in order for data to be collected in a variety of weather conditions as well. After testing and observation, it is strongly suggested that each location the device will be implemented, images are collected of the environment and of the trains which travel on the particular route for some time before testing the performance of the detection algorithm.

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